

I d i o s y n c r a s y :
Multi – world expressions.

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I d i o s y n e r a s y :

**“Traits, temperament,
character, etc.,
distinctive and specific
to an individual or a
collective”**
Spanish Royal Academic.

Popular Republic of China.

中国 (*Zhōngguó*).

Before the foundation of the PRCh...

**XVII to XI b.C. to
1368-1644**

**Raising of agriculture, metal smelting,
schools of philosophy, industry and
commerce, Buddhism and arts.**

Decayed of last dynasty. (Qing- 1644: 1911)

- **1st Opium War. (1840).**
- **2ndo Opium War (1860).**
- **Foundation of the Chinese Communist Party. (1921).**
- **Japanese invasion. (1937).**

After the foundation of PRCh...

Foundation of PRCh. (October 1st 1949).

- **Mao era (1949 – 1976).**
- **Industry promotion (10 years)**
- **Cultural Revolution 1966.**

Opening to Chinese market (1978).

- **Deng Xiaoping is in power again (1977).**
- **Tian'anmen's killing 1989.**
- **Advocated socialist market 1993.**
- **China enters to WTO: 2001.**

In China *the family* is the foundation for unity in the society.

In modern Chinese, the word “guo jia” is also used to name “State”. This word joined with the word “jia” become family in Chinese. The character “guo” means: National Space.

国家

Writing

How many character does exist?

Simplified Chinese has more than 50,000 characters:

- Only 10,000 are used.
- 3,500 are commonly use.
- 1,000 are essential to understand colloquial language.

Is it important the size of the strokes in each character?

It is important. A word with completely different meaning can be written in the same exact way, but the length, the position and the next character determined the meaning of the word.

What are the main characteristics of Chinese language?

- The radicals are the 214 basic symbols for themselves or placed within the classified Chinese characters.

人 友

rén
Person

yǒu
Friend

愛

ài
Love

心

xīn
Heart

女人

Nǚ rén
Women

美女

Měi Nǚ
Beauty

Painting & Poetry

Dynasty T'ang (618-907) is considered the *golden age* for this art. The paintings with mountains, forests and gardens reflects peace and harmony. That is why views were always used by writes.

The three categories from the principal Chinese painting includes: views, flowers and birds.

Throughout of the evolution of Chinese poetry, it is often associate with painting and calligraphy. The three form an inseparable artistic expression.

Zhou Fang, (Dynasty Tang)

Emperor Ming
Huang's Flight
to Sichuan
(por Li
Zhaodao, Tang
Dynasty)

- **Capital City:** Beijing
- **Coin:** 1 Yuan = 1.77 pesos
- **22 providences:** Anhui, Fujian, Gansu, Guangdong, Guizhou, Hainan, Hebei, Heilongjiang, Henan, Hubei, Hunan, Jiangsu, Jiangxi, Jilin, Liaoning, Qinghai, Shaanxi, Shandong, Shanxi, Sichuan, Yunnan, Zhejiang.
- **5 Autonomous Regions:** Guangxi, Mongolia Interior, Ningxia, Xinjiang & Xizang (Tibet).
- **2 Special Administrative Regions:** Hong Kong & Macao.

Administrative Divisions of the People's Republic of China (PRC)

Dali City (Yunnan)

All the city conserves the original architecture. It is well visited by the “westerns” to enjoy the view and the ancient life style.

Dunhuang (Gansu)

It is the first place to receive the extension from Buddhism from India. It has numerous carved mountains from 1,000 years old. Each represents the philosophy, the music, dancing, education, etc.

Potala Palace (Tibet)

It is located at the hills of Lhasa. Walls has 117 meters of high with the roof of gold. Potala is divided in 2 sections: Red Palace (religious place) and White palace (Dalai Lama's rooms). It also has a mural gallery painted on the walls.

Great Wall.

It is 4,000 miles long and it was built by hand for over one million people. The purpose was to protect the city against invaders. (Qing dynasty: 221 - 206 A.C.).

Temple of Heaven

It is the biggest religious complex. It was built in the Ming & Qing dynasty where the emperors used to attend to worship the heaven for wealth harvest and other rituals. The architecture reflects the fengshui philosophy.

Forbidden City

Place where the emperors from dynasties Ming & Qing lived. It is protected by high walls and four fosses around the city.

Three Gorges Dam (Hubei)

The Three Gorges Dam is the world's largest capacity hydroelectric power station. The dam increases the Yangtze River's shipping capacity, and reduces the potential for floods downstream by providing flood storage space.

Terracotta Warriors (Shaanxi)

It has a reproduction of warriors and imperial horses. They were buried together with the emperor. It has 14,000 square meters and 3 big holes with a total number of 6,000 figures.

Tiananmen Square

**"Gate of God's peace."
It was built during the Ming dynasty. It measures 880 meters by 500 meters, making it the largest square in the world**

新年好

xīn nián hǎo

**It is know as: Lunar New Year Festival.
(Lunar Calendar).
The festival last three weeks.**

1sr day	2do day	3rd day.
It pays homage to ancestors.	The married daughters return home from their parents	People prepare offerings of food to receive the return of the Kitchen God.

Buddhism

Buddhism believes in people and there is not aggression against any other religion. It leads to people to achieve the highest happiness in life and after it.

The best time for Buddhism was during Tang dynasty. Emperors used to spend their money in building monasteries and Buddhism sculptures.

In addition, Buddhism promotes a code of conduct which is known as the Five Precepts: killing, stalling, lying, consuming alcohol and satisfying whims.

Jade Buda. Buddhist Temple, Shanghai, China

Confucianism

Confucians see the cosmos as something harmonious regulating stations, wildlife, plants and human. If this harmony was disrupted, would have serious consequences.

A common example used by Confucianism is the bad governor who leads his people to ruin by their conduct.

Poor governance contrary violates the natural order and the Mandate of Heaven.

Taoism

It is an esoteric philosophy which explores and develops the second of the primitive religions of China: the cult of nature, advocating the integration of man in nature, and the removal of government affairs.

The symbol of Yin & Yang was created by Taoism. They represents two opposite forces in constant conflict with one another. This notion of two opposite poles and the permanence of change is common in Chinese thought through its culture and history.

सत्यमेव जयते

Republic of India

भारत गणराज्य *Bhārat Gaṇ arājya*

History

India's culture is marked by a high degree of pluralism. India has a continuously recorded history for over *2,500* years.

The Indian culture took a distinctive shape during the 11th century BCE. It has roots based in the Indus Valley Tradition,

Vedic age which laid the foundation of Hindu philosophy, mythology, literary tradition and beliefs and practices, such as dhárma, kárma, yóga and mokṣa

History of South Asia

Stone Age	before 3300 BCE
Mature Harappan	2600–1700 BCE
Late Harappan	1700–1300 BCE
Iron Age	1200–300 BCE
Maurya Empire	321–184 BCE
Middle Kingdoms	230 BCE–1279 CE
Satavahana	230 BCE–220 CE
Gupta Empire	280–550 CE
Pala Empire	750–1140 CE
Delhi Sultanate	1206–1596
Mughal Empire	1526–1803
Maratha Empire	1674–1818
British India	1858–1947
Modern States	since 1947

[Timeline](#)

C a s t S y s t e m

“Heritage system of social stratification (2,500 years ago). Hinduism teaches that society was created from the body of the divinity: **Brahmā**.”

Her struggle for justice against honour killing

Sushma's brother murdered her husband, three others to avenge their marriage

Divya Gandhi

BANGALORE: As the Women's Reservation Bill rings in the centennial year of Women's Day on a celebratory note, 25-year-old Sushma Tiwari's story tells of an inspirational fight-back against a brutal form of patriarchy and caste oppression.

It has been a six-year legal battle for Sushma against the horrific 'honour killing' by her brother of almost her entire marital family: husband Prabhu Nochil, her father-in-law and two minors in their home near Mumbai, all to avenge her marriage into a family of a 'lower' caste. Sushma is from a Brahmin family of UP, and Prabhu, an Ezhava from Kerala.

Although the fast track sessions court in Maharashtra, and later the Bombay High Court, awarded the death penalty to Sushma's brother Dilip Tiwari and his accomplices, the Supreme Court in December 2009 reduced the sentence to 25-year imprisonment.

This February, Sushma filed a review petition questioning the decision to let the perpetrators of this crime.

In 2004, seven months after the couple got married, Dilip and his accomplices

Sushma Tiwari in Bangalore on Thursday. — PHOTO: BHAGYA PRAKASH K.

the caste, community, religion, though totally unjustified, is a stark reality."

"Totally illegal"

Sushma has challenged this reasoning, stating this perception "is wrong and totally illegal under our Constitution and various laws of the land like the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989" and "can never be made a ground for lessening a sentence. In fact, these feelings of caste hatred are themselves criminal..."

Her petition states: "In fact, mass killings based on the concept of 'honour' must be viewed by this Hon'ble Court as murders which must be given the highest deterrent sentence."

In Bangalore recently to attend the National Young Women's convention organised by the All India Democratic Women's Association (AIDWA), this resolute young woman told *The Hindu* that by reducing the sentence, the highest court of the land has sent out a wrong message to all those who are deterred out of caste-hatred sake of hu-

four members of the family, and grievously injured others. A pregnant woman was killed. Sushma's brother Dilip Tiwari and his accomplices, the Supreme Court in December 2009 reduced the sentence to 25-year imprisonment.

a common experience that when the young sister commits something unusual and [an] affair."

It added: "If he became the victim of his wrong genuine caste conflict it would..."

TE SOCIETY
W tab
a relative.
Court, ex
ts decision to revoke
entence, said: "It is

PHOTO: BHAGYA PRAKASH K.

We don't need no (sex) education

We can no longer afford to dwell in the corridor of uncertainty when it comes to sex and sexuality...

CAN WE REALLY LEAVE IT TO TIME AND NATURE?

PHOTO: ANU PUSHKARNA

Religion

India is known as the land of spirituality and philosophy. Indian religions form one of the most defining aspects of Indian culture. Major dhármic religions which were founded in India including: Hinduism, Buddhism and Jainism.

The most dominant religion in India today is Hinduism.

R e l i g i o n

Hinduism

It grants absolute and complete freedom of belief and worship. It conceives the whole world as a single family that worships the one truth, and therefore it accepts all forms of beliefs of distinct religions.

Prominent themes in Hindu beliefs include:

- **Dharma** (ethics/duties),
- **Samsāra** (The continuing cycle of birth, life, death and rebirth),
- **Karma** (action and subsequent reaction),
- **Moksha** (liberation from samsara),
- **Yogas** (paths or practices).

Religion

Hinduism

According to Hinduism, three Lords rule the world:

Brahma: The Creator.

Sarasvati:

“Goddess of learning”.

Vishnu: The Preserver.

Lakshmi;

“Wealth and prosperity”.

Shiva: The Destroyer.

Parvati

“Goddess of Power”

Religion

- Hindus can engage in pūjā (worship or veneration), either at home or at a temple.

- Devout Hindus perform daily chores such as worshiping at dawn after bathing.

- Notable feature in religious ritual is the division between purity and pollution.

- Hindus advocate the practice of *ahimsā* (non-violence) and respect for all life because divinity is believed to permeate all beings, including plants and non-human animals.

VENTING THEIR IRE: Indian students and supporters stage a rally in Melbourne on Sunday condemning the recent attacks on the Indian student community and demanding justice for the victims of the assaults. The "peace rally," which kicked off from outside the Royal Melbourne Hospital, saw chanting of slogans such as "Bharat Mata Ki Jai."

Festivals

Diwali

It involves the lighting of small clay lamps filled with oil to signify the triumph of good over evil. Diwali commemorates the return of Lord Rama, along with Sita and Lakshmana, from his fourteen-year-long exile and vanquishing the demon-king Ravana.

Ganesh Chaturthi

It is the Hindu festival of Ganesha, the son of Shiva and Parvati, that celebrates the birthday of Ganesha who is widely worshipped as the god of wisdom, prosperity and good fortune.

Regal splendour

DEVOTEE'S DELIGHT: Priest of Sri Lakshmi Ganapati temple on NH 5 near Thatichetlapalem Balu Swamy giving the finishing touches to 'Raja alankaram' of Ganesha idol on the final day of Ganesha Navaratri in Visakhapatnam on Monday. - PHOTO: C. V. SUBRAHMANYAM

Festivals

Ugadi

It is the New Year's Day for the people of the Deccan region of India. It falls on the different day every year because the Hindu calendar is a lunisolar calendar. Ugadi marks the first day of the new year.

Thai Pongal

Thai Pongal, celebrated at harvest time, is traditionally intended to thank the Sun God and farmstead livestock that helped create the material abundance.

Festivals

Holi

Bonfires are lit in memory of the miraculous escape of young Prahlad accomplished when Demoness Holika, carried him into the fire. Prahlad escaped without any injuries due to his unshakable devotion.

It is celebrated by people throwing colored powder and colored water at each other.

Durga Puja

She went to battle on her ferocious mount lion, and killed the evil Mahishasura and restored heaven to the Gods. Durga Puja is observed in her honor, to celebrate her victory over evil.

CELEBRATION TIME: Schoolgirls perform the traditional Punjabi folk dance of giddha on the eve of the Basant Panchami in Amritsar on Friday. The festival marks the start of the spring season after the rigours of winter. PHOTO: AP

We'll not spare dating couples on Valentine's Day: Muthalik

Bangalore Bureau

BANGALORE: After their recent attack on young women at a Mangalore pub, the Sri Ram Sene has now announced an action plan to target couples found dating on February 14, Valentine's Day.

At a press conference here on Thursday, Sri Ram Sene leader Pramod Muthalik, who is now on bail, said Sene activists across Karnataka would not only hold protests outside

colleges, hostels and hotels, where Valentine's Day celebrations are held, but also forcibly marry off couples found dating in public.

"Our activists will go around with a priest, a turmeric stub and a 'māngal sutra' on February 14. If we come across couples being together in public and expressing their love, we will take them to the nearest temple and conduct their marriage," he said. If the couples resisted

the move, the girl would be forced to tie a 'rakhi' to the boy.

Mr. Muthalik said his outfit would ensure that Valentine's Day greeting cards were not sold. Activists would check out stores that sold such cards.

Asked if his men would use physical force against those celebrating Valentine's Day, Mr. Muthalik said they "will not take the law into their own hands."

Music, Dance & Cinema

Indian music covers a wide range of traditions and regional styles. Classical music largely encompasses the two genres - North Indian Hindustani, South Indian Carnatic traditions and their various offshoots in the form of regional folk music.

The Indian film industry is the largest in the world.

Bollywood, based in Mumbai, makes commercial Hindi films and is the most prolific film industry in the world.

Indian dance too has diverse folk and classical forms. Eight dance forms, many with narrative forms and mythological elements, have been accorded classical dance status by India's National Academy of Music, Dance, and Drama.

Ringa, Ringa, Ringaaa

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Multi – world expressions.

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T H A N K Y O U !